

WATER DISPERSABILITY OF PAPERS– BALANCING MATERIAL STRENGTH AND DISPERSIBILITY

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Abstract: *Water- dispersability of papers is useful in various applications as it disintegrates into its fibers after usage, and also is a fully biodegradable material. In this work, we have first introduced a test for the disintegration performance of different paper grades. Based on that disintegration and comprehensive statistical analysis we have performed a quantitative analysis on the technological and physical mechanisms responsible for a good paper dispersibility in water. Regarding technological parameters for paper production, we identified lignin content, degree of refining and addition of starch as relevant factors reducing paper dispersibility. Addition of a debonding agent, a surfactant, was not found to be effective here. In order to clarify the physical mechanisms governing paper disintegration behavior we analyzed paper properties related to mechanical strength and water uptake. We found a strong correlation between wet- and dry tensile strength of paper, both of which were highly affecting the dispersibility. Water uptake in the network, or water uptake into the fibers (WRV), or fiber wetting (contact angle) were not, or only very moderately, related to paper dispersibility. The only water absorption related paper property correlated to the disintegration results was liquid penetration speed measured with ultrasonic testing. We are concluding that the same mechanisms that are creating dry strength – high density and strong fiber-fiber bonding – are also responsible for a bad disintegration behavior. Principal component analysis revealed that paper strength and water penetration speed are not governed by different latent variables but instead are all strongly associated with the first principal component. This suggests that the same mechanisms are responsible for reduction of water penetration speed and wet/dry strength. A future solution*

of the problem might thus be to decouple network strength and water penetration, e.g. by identifying suitable additives that impart bonding strength to the network without reducing the access of water to break the fiber-fiber bonds.